

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF THE SPREAD OF PHYTOPATOGENIC FUNGI IN THE VEGETATIVE AND GENERATIVE ORGANS OF FODDER PLANTS (IN THE EXAMPLE OF ALFALFA PLANT)

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Abstract

The presented work is devoted to the study of the propagation characteristics of phytopathogenic fungi in both underground and aboveground vegetative and generative organs of cultivated fodder plants, including different varieties of alfalfa. It has been determined that, *Ascochyta viciae* Lib., *A.imperfecta* Peck., *A.trifolii* Bond., *Sclerotinia libertiana* Fuck., *Ustilago Zeae* Beck fungi can spread equally in all organs of the alfalfa plant, that is, in both vegetative and generative organs. They are also called “universal fungi”. At the same time, it was known that *Microsporum commune* Rabh., *Fusarium oxysporium* Schl and *F. bulbigenum* Cke et Mass fungi infect only the leaf, *Rhizopus nodosus* Namysi only the flower, and *Pythium de baryanum* Hess, *Fusarium sporotrichiella* Sacc only the root. These are called “specific fungi”. Also, comparison of vegetative and generative organs of alfalfa plant shows that leaves are most infected with diseases.

Keywords: fodder plant, vegetative organ, generative organ, phytopathogenic fungus, “universal fungi”, “specific fungi”, plant disease.

Introduction. In modern times, the demand for cultivated agricultural plants, including fodder plants, which are of economic importance, is constantly increasing. Thus, the fact that fodder plants, especially cultivated alfalfa are rich in plant protein, fix the free nitrogen of the atmosphere and transform it into nitrogen compounds in the soil, not only increases its importance as a fodder plant, lent also greatly increases the productivity of the soil [1; 2; 3]. However, in recent times, the disturbance of the bioecological balance has led to the activation of organisms forming a number of ecological groups in the environment, especially photopathogenic fungi. This, in turn, leads to a 15-30% decrease in productivity, which directly or indirectly affects the productivity of cultivated fodder plants [4; 8]. In this regard, the use of technical, agrotechnical, chemical and biological control methods of fodder plants, including the cultivated alfalfa plant, not separately, lent in a complex manner, has been experimentally confirmed in the conducted research and considered suitable for the purpose.

Objective. The purpose of the presented work was to study the specific interactions between the cultivated fodder plant and photopathogenic fungi, and the characteristics of their spread on the vegetative and generative organs of the plant.

Materials and methods. Researches were carried out in fields where alfalfa is grown in Bilasuvar and

Saatli regions. It should be noted that the alfalfa plant was intensively watered during cultivation, depending on the stage of the vegetation period. Cultivated varieties with high productivity, including Absheron, Lider, Goyazan, black alfalfa, etc. The samples were taken from both above-ground and underground vegetative and generative organs of cultivated alfalfa. Which as an underground organ of the alfalfa plant, was taken both from the root and around the root, i.e from the rhizosphere.

At the same time, samples were obtained from the above-ground organs of the alfalfa plant, including stems, leaves, flowers and seeds. Planned route and stationary observation methods, which are widely used in mycology, were used for sampling. It should be noted that sampling was carried out in different seasons of the year and in different phases of the alfalfa vegetation period. In the course of research more than 950 samples of 4 varieties of alfalfa were taken and mycological examinations were carried out [5; 6; 7; 9].

The obtained results and their discussion. In the course of the research, it became clear that the distribution of phytopathogenic fungi living on the cultivated alfalfa plant and considered to be the causative agent of this or that pathology on the vegetative and generative organs of the host plant differs sharply from each other. So, *Ascochyta viciae* Lib., *A.imperfecta* Peck., *A.trifolii* Bond., white rot agent, *Sclerotinia libertiana*

Fuck., powdery mildew agent, *Ustilago Zeae Beck*, which are the causative agents of ascycytosis pathology. They are equally distributed in almost all vegetative and reproductive organs of the alfalfa plant, respectively. In other words, such mushrooms are also called universal mushrooms.

But a number of fungi, including *Macrosporium commune Rabh.* “black mold”, *Fusarium oxysporium schl.*, settled only on the leaves of my clover plant and *F.bulbigenin Cke et Mass* “wilting” by infecting only the leaf organ, *Rhizopus nodosus Namysi* “dry rot” ley

infecting only the flower organ *Pithmu de Baryanum Hess*, *Fusarium sporotrichiella Sace*. Fungi settle only in the root organ and form “root throat” pathologies. In other words, such mushrooms are called “specific mushrooms”. Because these fungi show a selective attitude towards the organs they live on .

At the same time, comparing the vegetative and generative organs of the alfalfa plant according to the prevalence of pathologies, it is clear that the leaves are the organs most infected with diseases (Figure 1).

Figure1. Pathology recorded in vegetative and generative organs of alfalfa plant.

As can be seen from the picture, the generative organs of the alfalfa plant, especially the seeds, are considered to be the least susceptible to fungal diseases. In our opinion, as much as the settlement of pathogenic fungi on different organs of the plant, including alfalfa, depends on the functional activity of the plant organ, it also depends on the eco-biological characteristics of the fungus.

Conclusions. It should be noted that, regardless of the localization of fungi in any organ of the alfalfa plant, the pathologies they cause directly affect the physiology of the plant, thereby significantly reducing its productivity from the cultivated alfalfa plant, it is considered effective to use intensive cultivation technology, including proper tillage. In addition, in order to protect cultivated fodder plants from mycological pathologies, systematic mycological analyzes should be carried out and the phytosanitary situation should be evaluated.

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